

The Ethics of Tax Evasion in Islam: A Comment

Robert W. McGee¹

JEL Code: H26, D63

Abstract

According to Islam, Muslims have a moral obligation to pay zakat for the support of the poor and for the legitimate functions of government. Thus, evading one's duty to pay zakat is classified as an immoral act. The Islamic system of taxation is a voluntary one, at least partially, although Islamic literature makes it clear that a government is justified in forcing people to pay taxes if the amount raised by zakat is insufficient to cover all the legitimate costs of government. However, this right of interference with the individual's personal property will be limited to the extent required by the general welfare of the society. Also, it does not follow that Muslims have a moral obligation to pay whatever taxes the government demands and it does not follow that any and all forms of taxation are legitimate. Thus, a case can be made that some forms of tax evasion, under certain conditions, may not be immoral.

The author reviews the literature and discusses the circumstances where tax evasion would not be considered unethical under Islam.

¹ W. Paul Stillman School of Business, Seton Hall University. The author would like to thank the two anonymous reviewers for their comments and suggestions. The author may be reached at bob@dumontinst.com.

My distinguished colleagues have done a superb job of outlining the Islamic tax system in the previous article (Murtuza and Ghazanfar), so I will not rehash what they have already said. According to Islam, Muslims have a moral obligation to pay zakat for the support of the poor and for the legitimate functions of government. Thus, evading one's duty to pay zakat is classified as an immoral act. The Islamic system of taxation is a voluntary one, at least partially, although Islamic literature makes it clear that a government is justified in forcing people to pay taxes if the amount raised by zakat is insufficient to cover all the legitimate costs of government. However, "This right of interference with the individual's personal property will be limited to the extent required by the general welfare of the society ..." (Ahmad: 134).

Also, it does not follow that Muslims have a moral obligation to pay whatever taxes the government demands (Yusuf: 96), and it does not follow that any and all forms of taxation are legitimate. Thus, a case can be made that some forms of tax evasion, under certain conditions, may not be immoral. For example, if the government engages in activities that are beyond its legitimate functions, it might not be immoral to withhold taxes.² It might also not be immoral to evade certain kinds of taxes.

Ahmad (135-36) cites Yusuf's *Economic Justice in Islam*, which provides a list of practices that would be immoral for an Islamic state to engage in:

- (a) It is immoral on the part of the state to use its power and privilege to make monopolistic gains or to tax the common people indirectly for replenishing the exchequer thereby (Yusuf 96).
- (b) There is no room in Islam for custom barriers, restrictive tariffs or exchange control. The Islamic state, therefore, must not resort to them (Yusuf 68, 101).
- (c) It is illegitimate and unlawful for the state to tax directly or indirectly the general body of consumers and to give "protection" to the interests of a class of producers in the name of industrialization (Yusuf 9-10).

² For more on the legitimate role of the government under Islam, see Siddiqi.

- (d) Since it is the duty of the state to dispense justice free of charge, therefore, there must not be any court-fees, revenue stamps or fees of any kind for the transaction of any official business (Yusuf 67).
- (e) There must not be any "income" tax as such. Besides curbing the initiative it assumes illegitimacy of the income of the rich. The state should levy, if need be, a proportional tax on the pattern of zakat on the accumulated wealth of the capable tax-payers (Yusuf 67).³
- (f) The state should not resort to indirect taxation. If the state has to tax, then, it should do so directly so that the taxes represent a conscious contribution of the people to the cause of public interest (Yusuf 67).
- (g) That there is no justification for imposing death duty. Islamic laws of inheritance take care of the wealth left by the deceased (Yusuf 67).

If these are the parameters, then it would seemingly not be immoral for a Muslim not to pay indirect taxes, which include excise taxes, customs duties and perhaps corporate income taxes.⁴ Muslims could also morally evade paying tariffs and could engage in smuggling, as long as the good smuggled is not against Islam, such as alcohol or cocaine. Evading income taxes would also not

³ Since there must not be any income tax, there definitely must not be any graduated income tax, which necessarily treats the rich less favorably than the poor. According to Yusuf (p. 67): "There is no tax on income, which curbs initiative and enterprise. The progressive taxation assumes illegitimacy of the income of the rich. The rising slabs represent taxation with vendetta. Only a proportional tax at a fixed rate (on the pattern of Zakat) is to be levied on the accumulated wealth of the capable taxpayers without any distinction."

⁴ A simplified definition of a direct tax is a tax that individuals or corporations pay directly (Stiglitz 387). Indirect taxes are taxes on commodities. However, the burden of a corporate income tax is ultimately borne by individuals, either shareholders, consumers or the corporation's employees. So a case can be made that a corporate income tax is actually an indirect tax. For more on the distinction between direct and indirect taxes, as well as the ethics of tax evasion in general, see McGee (1994).

be immoral although evading a property tax might be. The evasion of inheritance, estate and gift taxes would not be immoral.

Ahmad elaborates on some of the points made by Yusuf. Protectionism is condemned because it amounts to a direct or indirect tax placed upon consumers by the state. The general public must pay higher prices because the favored few (domestic producers) are being enriched. Traders and consumers are not morally bound to pay the increased price, whether the price increase is the result of protectionism or price fixing (Ahmad: 122).

According to Ahmad, “the adoption of any methods that create an artificial rise in the prices is strictly forbidden.”(Ahmad: 123) Price fixing and protectionism are only two actions that cause prices to artificially rise. Other causes mentioned by Ahmad include the sales tax and excise taxes.

“The term *maks* is used for sales-tax. The Prophet (peace be on him) had reportedly said: ‘He who levies *maks* shall not enter Paradise’. Since the imposition of sales-tax (or, for that matter, of octroi and excise duties) results in raising the prices unjustly, therefore, Islam does not approve of it. The Caliph ‘Umar ibn ‘Abd al-’Aziz had abolished *maks*, interpreting it as *bakhs* (diminution in what is due to others) which is expressly prohibited by the Qur’an.”(Ahmad: 123)

This prohibition on sales taxes places Muslims in a bit of a quandary, since nearly every state in the USA levies a sales tax. Many European and other countries levy value-added taxes, which are basically the same thing as a sales tax. While it might be expedient for a Muslim consumer to pay a sales tax, and for a Muslim merchant to charge a sales tax, because they are required to do so by law, there is apparently nothing immoral about not collecting or paying them according to Islam.

Excise taxes are more difficult to avoid paying, since they are incorporated into the price of certain products. Of course, the excise tax on alcohol is easy to avoid. Just refrain from purchasing alcoholic beverages. But the excise tax on gasoline is more difficult (but not impossible) to avoid. In fact, the only way I can think of offhand to avoid paying the excise tax on gasoline is to buy gas from certain gas stations on Long Island, where the local mafia has made the evasion of the excise tax on gasoline into a profitable business. However, doing business with the mafia might run afoul of other Islamic tenets.

Another, less obvious form of tax evasion that is not immoral is the evasion of compliance with certain government regulations. A number of studies have pointed out that regulations can be equivalent to a tax,⁵ and many examples can be given. One of the more obvious examples is rent control. If a landlord who owns a rent controlled building is prohibited from charging more than \$500 a month for an apartment that would fetch \$1,500 in a free market, he is, in effect, being forced to subsidize his tenant to the tune of \$1,000 a month. The effect of this regulation is exactly the same as if the landlord were allowed to charge the \$1,500 market rate, then pay a tax of 66 2/3 percent. Rent control laws force the transfer of wealth from property owners to a favored group (tenants), which is immoral according to the tenets of Islam.

The strongest argument for complying with government regulations is when the regulation benefits the general public. However, many regulations are not of this genre. At least two other categories of regulations exist, those that benefit some special interest at the expense of the general public and those that are actually harmful to the general public. A number of trade regulations fall into one or both of these categories. The United

⁵ For examples, see Utt; Payne; Weidenbaum and DeFina; MacDonnell; U.S. General Accounting Office; Gray; Hopkins; Yandle; Adler.

States Trade Representative publishes a book each year that summarizes some of these protectionist regulations.⁶

Numerous studies in recent years have attempted to measure the cost of various regulations. Some of these studies have concluded that certain regulations cost more than they are worth, or actually do more damage than good.⁷

Since there is no moral obligation for a Muslim to comply with a law that causes prices to rise unnecessarily or that enhances the wealth of some protected group at the expense of the general public -- such as price fixing and protectionist trade legislation -- and since some regulations cause prices to rise unnecessarily or protect some favored group at the expense of the general public, it is logical to conclude that Muslims have no moral duty to comply with regulations that either cause prices to rise unnecessarily or that protect some special interest at the expense of the general public. It would also be logical to conclude that there is no moral duty for a Muslim (or anyone, for that matter) to comply with a regulation that is actually harmful to the general public.

Whether, and under what circumstances, a Muslim has a duty to evade certain taxes or regulations is a question we will leave for another day.

References

- Adler, Jonathan H. 1996. *Property Rights, Regulatory Takings, and Environmental Protection*. Washington, DC: Competitive Enterprise Institute.
- Ahmad, Mushtaq. 1995. *Business Ethics in Islam*. Islamabad, Pakistan: The International Institute of Islamic Thought and the International Institute of Islamic Economics.

⁶ For example, see United States Trade Representative, 1997 National Trade Estimate Report on FOREIGN TRADE BARRIERS (Washington, DC: Superintendent of Documents).

⁷ For a study that discusses some regulations that actually make things worse rather than better see Stroup and Goodman.

- Gray, Wayne B. 1987. The Cost of Regulation: OSHA, EPA and the Productivity Slowdown. *American Economic Review* 77: 998-1006.
- Hopkins, Thomas D. 1991. Cost of Regulation. An RIT Public Policy Working Paper, Rochester Institute of Technology.
- MacDonnell, Lawrence J. 1989. Government Mandated Costs: The regulatory burden of environmental, health and safety standards. *Resources Policy* 15(1): 75-100. March 1.
- McGee, Robert W. 1994. Is Tax Evasion Unethical? *The University of Kansas Law Review* 42:2 (Winter): 411-435.
- Murtuza, Athar and S.M. Ghazanfar. 1998. Tax as a Form of Worship: Exploring the Nature of Zakat. *Journal of Accounting, Ethics & Public Policy* 1:2 (Spring).
- Payne, James L. 1992. Unhappy Returns: The \$600-Billion Tax Ripoff. *Policy Review* (Winter): 18-24.
- Siddiqi, M. Nejatullah. 1996. *Role of the State in the Economy: An Islamic Perspective*. Leicester, UK: The Islamic Foundation.
- Stiglitz, Joseph E. 1988. *Economics of the Public Sector*, second edition. New York: W.W. Norton & Company.
- Stroup, Richard L. and John C. Goodman. 1989. Making the World Less Safe: The Unhealthy Trend in Health, Safety, and Environmental Regulation. NCPA Policy Report #137, Dallas: National Center for Policy Analysis.
- U.S. General Accounting Office. 1993. Regulatory Burden: Recent Studies, Industry Issues, and Agency Initiatives. GAO/GGD-94-28. December.
- Utt, Ronald. 1991. The Growing Regulatory Burden: At What Cost To America? IPI Policy Report No. 114, Lewisville, TX: Institute for Policy Innovation. November.
- Weidenbaum, Murray L. and Robert DeFina. 1978. The Cost of Federal Regulation of Economic Activity. Washington, DC: American Enterprise Institute. May.
- Yandle, Bruce. 1994. Regulatory Takings, Farmers, Ranchers and the Fifth Amendment. Center for Policy Studies, Clemson University.
- Yusuf, S.M. 1971. Economic Justice in Islam. Lahore: Sh. Muhammad Ashraf.